

erinha

European Research Infrastructure
on Highly Pathogenic Agents

ERINHA AISBL CoARA Action Plan

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Introduction

As a service-providing Research Infrastructure, a landmark on the ESFRI roadmap, and coordinator of large projects including **ISIDORe** that includes cascade-funding, research assessment is important for ERINHA. ERINHA will strive to work with its Members, policymakers and funders to promote responsible research assessment and support the reform of research assessment within the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

In its first part, this action plan includes. **the actions towards the design and implementation of the Agreement on Reforming Research**

In its second part, it focuses on the **longer-term actions** that should be carried out to contribute to the reform of research assessment by studying, developing and promoting the use of assessment practices aligned with CoARA commitments.

Actions at the institutional level

Revision of institutional indicators for benchmarking: Identify and promote the use of qualitative indicators and new, or an evolution of, metrics to complement the responsible use of quantitative indicators in the assessment of diverse scientific outputs.

Actions at the individual level

Revision of processes and criteria in research assessment:
Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and evaluation of researchers and professionals at the interface of science (e.g. Research managers and administrators, core facilities) at all career stages.

Ongoing actions

➤ 1. Raise awareness about CoARA & the reform of research assessment

- 1.1 Inform internally in ERINHA about CoARA
- 1.2 Inform internally in ERINHA about the advancements in the reform of research assessment.
- 1.3 Provide internal opportunities for ERINHA researchers to engage in research assessment discussion
- 1.4 Act as ambassadors for CoARA and the reform of research assessment when possible.

➤ 2. Actively promote advancements in research assessment

- 2.1 Promote & contribute to the discussion towards the reform of the research assessment system
- 2.2 Promote the use of practices in research assessment aligned with DORA and CoARA
- 2.3 Promote dialogue between the scientific community and policy makers in research assessment.

Longer-term actions

▶ 3. Actively promote advancements in research assessment

3.1 ERINHA level: Identify and promote the use of qualitative indicators and new, or an evolution of, metrics to complement the responsible use of quantitative indicators in the assessment of diverse scientific outputs from our Members and those benefiting from support through the project ERINHA coordinates.

3.2 Individual level (researchers): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of researchers in all career stages

3.3 Individual level (core facilities staff): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of core facilities personnel in all career stages

3.4 Individual level (research managers and administrators): Collect information and develop recommendations aligned with CoARA principles and commitments on the institutional policies for recruitment and career evaluation of research managers and administrators in all career stages.

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